

Synthesis of New Substituted Enamines from *N*-Methylacetoacetamide[†]

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Various substituted new enamines have been synthesised by azeotropic distillation of *N*-methylacetoacetamide with various secondary heterocyclic, aryl and aralkylamines. The products have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data.

ENAMINES are versatile synthetic intermediates particularly in the construction of heterocyclic compounds¹. The preparation of enamines from ketones and aldehydes is well-documented². However, no attempt has apparently been made to study the preparation of the enamines from *N*-methylacetoacetamide. So, it was felt worthwhile to undertake the synthesis of the title compounds for further investigations.

In the present study, a number of β -(substituted secondary heterocyclic, aryl and aralkylamino)-*N*-methylcrotonamides of the general structures **2** and **3** (Scheme 1) have been prepared according to the reported methods². The structures of the compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillaries using an Edmund Bühler melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds were checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates using iodine as chromogen. Ir (KBr and CHCl_3) spectra were recorded on a

Perkin-Elmer 283 B, spectrophotometer model, pmr spectra on a JEOL FX-90 Q FT spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a VG micromass 7070H instrument. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

The following procedure forms a general method for the synthesis of compounds presented in Tables 1 and 2.

*β -(Morpholino)-*N*-methylcrotonamide (2)*: A solution of *N*-methylacetoacetamide (11.5 g, 0.1 mol) and freshly distilled morpholine (8.7 g, 0.1 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was taken in a Dean-Stark apparatus and refluxed in an oil-bath. The course of reaction was followed by noting the amount of water collected. The solvent was removed on rotary evaporator and the product on trituration with ether gave *β -(morpholino)-*N*-methylcrotonamide* which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) (10.3 g, 55%), m.p. 102–03° (Found: C, 58.92; H, 8.91; N, 15.40. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 58.67; H, 8.75; N, 15.21%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 605 (C=C) and 1 590 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CDCl_3) (*Z*)-isomer 2.45 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.80–2.90 (3H, d, N- CH_2), 3.05–3.25 (4H, m, CH_2 towards N), 3.70–3.80 (4H, m, CH_2 towards O), 4.40 (1H, s, CH) and 5.70 (1H, b, NH); (*E*)-isomer δ 2.30 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.85–2.95 (3H, d, N- CH_2), 3.45 (1H, s, CH), 3.10–3.30 (4H, m, CH_2 towards N), 3.70–3.80 (4H, m, CH_2 towards O) and 5.70 (1H, b, NH); m/z 184 (M^+) (Calcd. 184).

The physical and spectral data of compounds (**2**); sl. nos. 4–6) are presented in Table 1.

*β -(α -Ethylbenzylamino)-*N*-methylcrotonamide (3)*: A mixture of *N*-methylacetoacetamide (11.5 g, 0.1 mol), freshly distilled α -ethylbenzylamine (13.5 g, 0.1 mol) and small amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.8 g, 0.0042 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed azeotropically as described above. After removal of the solvent, the resulting liquid was fractionated under reduced pressure to get the above compound as a pale yellow liquid, b.p. 152–54°/0.2–03 mm, which upon treatment with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) gave colourless crystals

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF β -(SECONDARY HETEROCYCLIC AMINO)-*N*-METHYLCROTONAMIDES

Sl. no.	$-\overset{\text{N}}{\text{Z}}-$	M.p. °C B.p. °C/mm	Yield %	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	δ (ppm)
4.	$-\text{N}(\text{OH}_2)_2$	100-02/0.6	63	C ₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	3 300(NH), 1 610(C=O), 1 570(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) (<i>Z</i>)-isomer 2.30 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80-2.90 (3H, d, N-CH ₃), 4.50 (1H, s, CH), 6.30 (1H, b, NH), (<i>E</i>)-isomer 2.50 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.85-2.95 (3H, d, N-CH ₃), 3.50 (1H, s, CH), 3.90 (1H, b, NH)
5.	$-\text{N}$ -Piperidine	86-87	63	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	3 300(NH), 1 630(C=O), 1 550(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) (<i>Z</i>)-isomer 1.50-1.75 (6H, m, CH ₂ piperidine), 2.50 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.81-2.91 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 3.15-3.35 (4H, m, CH ₂ towards N), 4.80 (1H, s, CH ₃), 5.60 (1H, b, NH), (<i>E</i>)-isomer 2.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.85-2.95 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 4.80 (1H, s, CH), 5.60 (1H, b, NH)
6	$-\text{N}$ -Pyrrolidine	195-96	70	C ₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	3 400(NH), 1 610(C=C), 1 580(C=O)	(ODCl ₃) (<i>Z</i>)-isomer 1.85-2.15 (4H, m, CH ₂ pyrrolidine), 2.55 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.85-2.95 (3H, d, N-CH ₃), 3.21-3.50 (4H, m, CH ₂ towards N), 4.45 (1H, s, CH), 5.20 (1H, b, NH); (<i>E</i>)-isomer 2.30 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.90-3.00 (3H, d, N-CH ₃), 4.45 (1H, s, CH), 5.20 (1H, b, NH)

(14.5 g, 62.5%), m.p. 80-81° (Found: C, 72.59; H, 8.89; N, 12.27. C₁₄H₂₀N₂O requires: C, 72.38; H, 8.67; N, 12.05%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 285 (NH), 1 615 (C=C), 1 580 (C=O) and 1 230 cm⁻¹ (C-N); δ (CDCl₃) 0.93 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.70 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 1.70 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.80-2.90 (3H, d, *J* 5 Hz, N-CH₃), 4.40 (1H, t, CH of CH₂-CH₃), 4.40 (1H, s, CH), 5.50 (1H, b, NH), 7.20-7.40 (5H, m, ArH) and 10.05 (1H, b, NH); *m/z* 232 (*M*⁺) (Calcd. 232).

Physical characteristics of the compounds (3; sl. nos. 7-21) are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The nmr spectra reveal that the new substituted crotonamides were a mixture of (*Z*)- and (*E*)-isomers. Spectra of (*Z*)-isomers of compounds

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF β -(SUBSTITUTED ARYL AND ALKYLAMINO)-*N*-METHYLCROTONAMIDES

Sl. no	R	M.p. °C B.p. °C/mm	Yield %	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	δ (ppm)
7.	C ₆ H ₅	88-89/ 0.3-0.4	66	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	3 460(NH), 1 610(C=O), 1 520(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) (<i>Z</i>)-isomer 2.25 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.75-2.85 (3H, d, N-CH ₃), 4.50 (1H, s, CH), 6.34 (1H, b, NH), 7.00-7.30 (5H, m, ArH), 11.20 (1H, b, NH), (<i>E</i>)-isomer 2.00 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.35 (1H, s, CH), 6.34 (1H, b, NH), 7.00-7.30 (5H, m, ArH), 11.20 (1H, b, NH)
8.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	68-70/ 0.4	59	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	3 465(NH), 1 650(C=C), 1 520(C=O)	(CCl ₄) (<i>Z</i>)-isomer 1.95 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.25 (3H, s, <i>p</i> -CH ₃ -ArH), 2.65-2.75 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 4.45 (1H, s, CH), 5.95 (1H, b, NH), 6.80-7.05 (4H, m, ArH), 11.05 (1H, s, NH), (<i>E</i>)-isomer 2.15 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.25 (3H, s, <i>p</i> -CH ₃ -ArH), 2.65-2.75 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 3.25 (1H, s, CH), 5.95 (1H, b, NH), 6.80-7.05 (4H, m, ArH), 11.05 (1H, s, NH)
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	95-97	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O	3 460(NH), 1 650(C=C), 1 580(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) (<i>Z</i>)-isomer 2.10 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.85-2.95 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 4.65 (1H, s, CH), 6.40 (1H, b, NH), 7.01-7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 11.55 (1H, b, NH), (<i>E</i>)-isomer 2.30 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.85-2.95 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-CH ₃), 3.50 (1H, s, CH), 6.40 (1H, b, NH), 7.01-7.50 (4H, m, ArH), 11.55 (1H, b, NH)

(Table 2 contd.)

10.	$C_6H_5OH_2-$	51-52	59	$C_{11}H_{18}N_2O$	3 470(NH), 1 620(C=O), 1 590(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) 1.85 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.75-2.85 (3H, d, N-OH ₂), 4.30 (1H, s, CH), 4.35-4.50 (2H, d, CH ₂), 5.70 (1H, b, NH), 7.30-7.50 (5H, m, ArH)
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	75-76	70	$C_{11}H_{18}N_2O$	3 465(NH), 1 650(C=O), 1 520(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) 1.95 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.25 (3H, s, <i>p</i> -CH ₃ -ArH), 2.65-2.75 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 4.45 (1H, s, CH), 5.95 (1H, b, NH), 6.60-7.05 (4H, m, ArH), 11.05 (1H, s, NH)
12.		107-08	68	$C_{13}H_{16}N_2O_2$	3 355(NH), 1 612(C=C), 1 580(C=O)	(CDCl ₃ +DMSO) 1.70 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.80-2.90 (3H, d, N-OH ₂), 4.35 (1H, s, CH), 4.51 (2H, s, CH ₂ Ar), 5.30 (1H, b, NH), 6.1 (2H, s, O-CH ₂ -O), 7.21-7.31 (4H, m, ArH), 9.80 (1H, b, NH)
13.	$C_6H_5.OH(CH_2)-$	153-54/ 0.5	65	$C_{11}H_{18}N_2O$	3 285(NH), 1 620(C=O), 1 590(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) (<i>Z</i>)-isomer 1.50-1.60 (3H, d, α -CH ₃), 1.8 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80-2.90 (3H, d, N-OH ₂), 4.30 (1H, s, CH), 4.40-4.70 (1H, q, CH-OH ₂), 7.40 (5H, s, ArH), 9.80 (1H, b, NH); (<i>E</i>)-isomer 1.80 (3H, s, CH ₃), 1.85 (1H, s, CH), 4.4-4.7 (1H, q, CH-OH ₂), 7.40 (5H, s, ArH), 9.8 (1H, b, NH)
14.	3,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ CH(OH ₂)-	74-75	42	$C_{11}H_{16}Cl_2N_2O$	3 300(NH), 1 615(C=O), 1 590(C=O)	(CCl ₄) 1.50-1.65 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, α -CH ₃), 1.60 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.90-3.00 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 4.50 (1H, s, CH), 4.56-4.90 (1H, q, CH, α -OH ₂), 5.30 (1H, b, NH), 7.30-7.60 (3H, m, ArH), 7.70 (1H, s, NH)
15.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ CH(C ₂ H ₅)-	59-60	59	$C_{14}H_{19}ClN_2O$	3 450(NH), 1 615(C=O), 1 590(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) 0.85-1.15 (3H, t, OH ₂), 1.70-1.90 (2H, q, CH ₂ -O ₂ H ₅), 1.80 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80-2.85 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 4.20 (1H, s, CH), 4.25-4.45 (3H, t, CH-C ₂ H ₅), 5.01 (1H, b, NH), 7.20-7.40 (4H, m, ArH)
16.	$C_6H_5CH(n-C_3H_7)-$	90-91	70	$C_{15}H_{22}N_2O$	3 330(NH), 1 620(C=O), 1 580(C=O)	(CCl ₄) 0.90-1.10 (7H, m, n-C ₃ H ₇), 1.60 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.70-2.80 (3H, d, N-OH ₂), 4.30 (1H, s, CH), 4.40 (1H, t, CH-C ₂ H ₅), 5.40 (1H, b, NH), 7.10-7.40 (5H, m, ArH), 9.80 (1H, b, NH)
17.	$C_6H_5CH_2CH_2-$	Decomp.	70	$C_{11}H_{18}N_2O$	3 370(NH), 1 620(C=O), 1 520(C=O)	(ODCl ₃) 1.75 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.75-2.85 (3H, d, N-OH ₂), 2.95-3.35 (2H, m, CH ₂), 4.35 (1H, s, CH), 5.35 (1H, b, NH), 7.01-7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 9.85 (1H, b, NH)
18.	$C_6H_5CH_2OH(C_6H_5)-$	Decomp.	68	$C_{21}H_{22}N_2O$	3 475(NH), 1 620(C=O), 1 590(C=O)	(ODCl ₃) 1.50 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.75-2.85 (3H, d, N-OH ₂), 3.01-3.10 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH ₂), 4.30 (1H, s, CH), 4.41-4.70 (1H, t, CH), 5.10 (1H, b, NH), 7.21-7.40 (10H, m, ArH), 10.70 (1H, b, NH)
19.	2,4-(OH ₂) ₂ - C ₆ H ₃ CH ₂ CH(C ₆ H ₅)-	Decomp.	65	$C_{21}H_{26}N_2O$	3 460(NH), 1 610(C=O), 1 580(C=O)	(CDCl ₃) 1.50 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.21-2.30 (6H, 2s, 2OH ₂ , ArH), 2.75-2.85 (3H, d, N-OH ₂), 2.91-3.10 (2H, t, OH ₂ -ArH), 4.25 (1H, s, CH), 4.75-5.0 (1H, q, OH), 7.21-7.40 (8H, m, ArH), 10.30 (1H, b, NH)
20.	<i>p</i> -O ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ - OH(C ₆ H ₅)-	Decomp.	60	$C_{21}H_{26}N_2O$	3 460(NH), 1 615(C=O), 1 645(C=O), (OHCl ₃)	(CCl ₄) 1.15 (3H, t, CH ₃ of C ₂ H ₅), 2.40-2.70 (4Hq, CH ₂ -OH ₂), 2.10 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.60-2.70 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 2.80-3.05 (2H, t, CH ₂ -Ar), 4.25 (1H, s, CH), 4.50 (1H, q, CH-OH ₂ Ar), 5.80 (1H, b, NH), 7.01-7.30 (9H, m, ArH), 9.90 (1H, b, NH)
21.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ CH(C ₆ H ₅)-	Decomp.	60	$C_{21}H_{21}N_2OCl$	3 465(NH), 1 615(C=O), 1 510(C=O), (OHCl ₃)	(ODCl ₃) 1.65 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.80-2.90 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz, N-OH ₂), 3.20 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7 Hz, CH ₂), 4.4 (1H, s, CH), 4.6-4.9 (1H, t, CH-CH ₂ -Ar), 5.30 (1H, b, NH), 7.20-7.60 (9H, m, ArH), 10.3 (1H, b, NH)

*C, H and N analyses were found satisfactory.

sl. nos. 4-6 (Table 1) and 7-9, 13 (Table 2) exhibited chemical shifts for C-CH₃ and vinylic C-H signals ranging from δ 1.80-2.25 to 4.30-4.80. Whereas in the (*E*)-isomers, position of the C-CH₃ and C-H signals range from δ 1.75-2.50 to 3.25-4.80 respectively.

The position of the vinylic proton is indicative of the degree of overlap between the electron pair on the nitrogen atom and the double bond. The greater the overlap, the higher is the field at which the vinylic proton appears.

In the ir spectra of new substituted enamines, the double bond stretching appears as a strong

band at 1 610-1 650 cm⁻¹. The high extinction coefficient for this absorption may be attributed to the overlap between the electron pair on the nitrogen atom and the π -electrons of the double bond.

References

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